

Modular and Composable Framework for Multipurpose Monitoring in Heterogeneous FPGA-Based Systems

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Abstract. Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) are increasingly used beyond edge applications, extending into cloud computing due to their high throughput and energy efficiency. Their integration with CPUs and GPUs in heterogeneous cloud-edge environments offers advantages but also introduces challenges in workload distribution, performance optimization, and power management. Addressing these challenges requires effective monitoring to ensure efficient resource utilization and system adaptability. However, principal existing solutions focus on debugging rather than comprehensive power-performance analysis. This paper presents a highly modular and composable framework for power-performance monitoring in FPGA-based System on Chip (SoC). Its architecture allows independent configuration and seamless interchange of components, enabling customized monitoring solutions tailored to specific workloads and deployment scenarios. This framework establishes a new standard for monitoring reconfigurable systems in heterogeneous cloud-edge deployments by offering flexibility, scalability, and compatibility, empowering developers to optimize performance and energy efficiency in complex computing environments.

Keywords: Monitoring · FPGA-Based Systems · Embedded Systems · Heterogeneous Systems

1 Introduction

FPGAs are expanding beyond traditional edge applications into cloud computing due to their high throughput and energy efficiency [3]. In heterogeneous cloud-edge infrastructures, they complement multicore processors and GPUs [6], offering enhanced computational efficiency and flexibility.

Effectively deploying applications across these diverse resources is challenging due to complex operational requirements. In this context, it is necessary to

address challenges such as functional verification, extracting performance metrics, managing workload distribution, and enabling continuous optimization. All of these require detailed resource and performance characterization. Since execution metrics vary dynamically based on workload conditions, design-time predictions are often insufficient, necessitating real-time insights for adaptive optimization and workload management. This paradigm change motivates the need for advanced and innovative monitoring methodologies.

Initially considered a debugging tool, monitoring has evolved into a strategic enabler for run-time performance analysis, facilitating optimizations such as workload redistribution [4] and operating condition adjustments [10].

However, most widely extended monitoring solutions remain limited in scope, primarily focused on debugging functionalities (e.g., AMD’s Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA), Intel’s Signal Tap Logic Analyzer) or platform-specific tools like the KRIA dashboard. These solutions lack cross-platform support, synchronized power-performance measurements, and detailed execution trace capturing, creating a gap in monitoring capabilities for FPGA System on Chips (SoCs).

To address these gaps, this work introduces a modular and composable power-performance monitoring framework tailored for FPGA SoCs. The framework ensures cross-platform compatibility, real-time synchronization of power and execution data, and comprehensive execution tracking across heterogeneous computing environments. Building upon the composability principles of Valente et al. [25], this work focuses on the coprocessor side of heterogeneous FPGA systems, offering unified access to a wide range of operational metrics/indicator, regardless of the underlying hardware configuration. By addressing long-standing gaps in monitoring solutions, the proposed framework empowers developers to optimize performance and efficiency in heterogeneous computing architectures.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents state-of-the-art works addressing integrated monitoring in reconfigurable systems. Section 3 introduces the proposed monitoring framework. Section 4 evaluates its performance and effectiveness. Finally, Section 5 concludes and outlines future research directions.

2 Related Work

The seminal work by Kornaros et al.[14] classified monitoring approaches for multi-purpose SoCs based on their objectives, including debugging, performance analysis, QoS, power management, fault tolerance, reliability, and security. Valente et al.[25] later expanded this classification to include highly specialized (vertical) monitoring solutions and the diverse components typically found on modern heterogeneous platforms. They emphasized the need for concurrent monitoring of multiple system aspects in cyber-physical systems, requiring seamless access to different architectural elements. They proposed a composable monitoring system to address this requirement, enabling uniform and transparent access across heterogeneous computing platforms.

Our proposed monitoring framework is based on a modular and composable design, enabling seamless integration of various FPGA-based coprocessors and

ensuring versatility and flexibility. However, effective monitoring extends beyond the programmable logic; capturing execution metrics from the embedded processing system (e.g., CPU cores and memory controller) in FPGA SoCs is equally crucial. This is particularly important in computing continuum environments, where computing nodes can be highly heterogeneous. The following subsection reviews the most relevant FPGA monitoring solutions in the state of the art.

2.1 Monitoring Resources and Applications running on FPGA

Although various solutions exist for monitoring memory, interconnects, and processing logic in FPGA-based heterogeneous environments [17,2,18,20,24], extending solutions to support coprocessor monitoring remains a challenge.

Commercial/proprietary solutions FPGA vendors such as AMD and Intel provide platform-specific monitoring tools. On the programmable logic side, AMD’s System Integrated Logic Analyzer (ILA)[26] and Intel’s Signal Tap Logic Analyzer[13] were designed for circuit debugging, allowing developers to analyze system behavior. However, these solutions introduce high resource overhead and require a host PC running proprietary software. Recently, AMD introduced `xmutil`⁴, a command-line utility for monitoring KRIA System-on-Modules (SOMs)⁵, which are also among the devices targeted in our work. `Xmutil` provides run-time metrics such as temperature, current, and power consumption. However, it lacks customization options, has a low sampling rate (1 sample/s), and can not be generalized to other devices.

Academic Contributions Several academic works have explored FPGA monitoring. Goeders et al.[11] introduced an HLS-based tool for automated instrumentation of debugging monitors, demonstrated on the LegUp HLS platform [5]. Similarly, Hammouda et al.[12] proposed an HLS tool that generates hardware systems with run-time verification monitors from C descriptions. However, neither work focuses on performance or power monitoring. Lee et al.[15] developed a system-level observation framework for run-time analysis and verification of processors and coprocessors, but without supporting power monitoring.

In contrast, power monitoring was the focus of Najem et al.[19] and Zoni et al.[29], who applied machine learning techniques at the RTL level to predict power-related metrics. However, their solutions lack portability, and adapting them to performance metrics would require significant re-engineering of the solution. Akgün et al. [1] used an Inter-Integrated Circuit (I²C)-based Power Management Bus protocol to retrieve voltage and current values for Dynamic Voltage and Frequency Scaling (DVFS). Their approach shares some components with our proposal but operates at a 5 ms sampling rate, whereas our framework achieves 1 μ s sampling.

For coarse-grained reconfigurable (CGR) coprocessors, Fanni et al.[9] extended the Performance API (PAPI)⁶, developing a configurable component for coprocessor-specific monitoring, focusing on latency and debugging. Encinas et

⁴ <https://github.com/Xilinx/xmutil>

⁵ <https://www.amd.com/en/products/system-on-modules/kria.html>

⁶ <https://icl.utk.edu/papi/>

al. [8] introduced a preliminary monitoring framework for power-performance correlation in ARTiCo³, a reconfigurable multi-accelerator infrastructure also used in our experiments. Power statistics for this architecture were further explored in Valente et al. [25].

To the best of our knowledge, none of these works has been demonstrated across multiple platforms or coprocessor architectures. In contrast, our work extends the modular and composable concept to coprocessor monitoring, aiming for broader applicability across heterogeneous systems.

3 Monitor Framework

The proposed monitoring framework, which has been made open source⁷, is detailed in this section, focusing on its components and how to easily configure it to different FPGA-based systems.

Fig. 1: Monitor framework.

3.1 Overview

The framework follows a modular design (see Figure 1), crucial to support flexible integration in heterogeneous systems. A customization layer lets users configure the power collection method, acceleration approach (e.g., start/stop-controlled, AXI-controlled) and device-specific settings. Interchangeable components are grouped into categories, allowing adaptation without altering the core structure. Trace formats are also configurable based on monitoring user-defined rules. Each layer compounding the system is described below.

⁷ <https://github.com/des-cei/fpga-monitor>

3.2 Monitored Traces

The framework supports monitoring of power consumption and performance in hardware-accelerated systems on the FPGA Programmable Logic (PL), along with power metrics from the Processing System (PS). While extensible to other metrics, these are prioritized for their relevance to run-time debugging and continuous optimization.

Power Consumption Many commercial FPGA boards include shunt resistors and onboard Analog to Digital Converters (ADCs), accessible via I²C. The framework provides a portable software stack to read these sensors, collecting timestamped power data into a local buffer with minimal integration effort. Device-specific I²C settings are configurable via TCL code or using the IP GUI. To overcome the limited sampling rate of I²C or in the event of the absence of onboard ADCs, the framework supports an external SPI-based measurement board with a custom Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) controller implemented in the FPGA fabric. As detailed in [7], this enables power measurements at up to 1 Msample/s, covering: i) full-board power (e.g., USB-powered devices), and ii) individual power rails, either via onboard or external shunt resistors. Data is stored in on-chip BRAMs of the device PL, and the entire acquisition process runs in parallel with system execution. For details, refer to [7]. The framework supports a wide range of monitoring setups through its on-chip I²C integration and high-speed external SPI interface. Moreover, its modular design and the use of standard protocols allow easy extension to custom on-board or external monitoring solutions.

Performance A minimal control protocol for hardware accelerators in FPGA-based systems consists of a 1-bit start/stop signal handshake on memory-mapped accelerator registers. Alternatively, this control might rely on bus handshakes, such as AXI Stream’s ready/valid protocol. The proposed framework enables users to register custom internal signal events with timestamps using dedicated hardware components (e.g., edge detectors, counters) in the FPGA fabric. If start/stop behavior is triggered by bus activity, equivalent 1-bit signals are generated to unify processing. While this work focuses on start/stop events, any internal signal can be monitored.

Power and performance traces are sampled in parallel along with associated timestamps, enabling accurate time alignment.

3.3 Computing Infrastructure

The interaction between control, monitoring, and hardware acceleration in heterogeneous systems can vary significantly depending on the computing platform underneath. The framework provides this diversity by supporting different control methods (e.g., hard-core CPU) and accelerator implementations (e.g., Vitis).

Platform’s Control The monitoring infrastructure is packed as an IP to be integrated in the FPGA fabric. IP logic includes a dedicated Finite State Machine (FSM) to coordinate the synchronized trace acquisition. It exposes control and status registers and features an AXI interface for both memory-mapped register access and trace retrieval via a Direct Memory Access (DMA)

controller. We assume a microprocessor is available to control the infrastructure, either as a hard-core processor in FPGA SoCs (e.g., the PS in AMD Xilinx devices), or as a soft-core processor when needed. In cloud scenarios, a host can also control the FPGA via a PCIe connection. The framework includes all required drivers and libraries to support these configurations, ensuring broad platform compatibility.

Acceleration Infrastructure The framework is agnostic to the hardware acceleration flavour in the reconfigurable system. As long as accelerators expose start/stop signals or are controlled via AXI buses (see section 3.2), they will be compatible with the proposed framework.

Compatibility has been validated with three representative frameworks: i) AMD Vitis, a commercial solution for FPGA-based acceleration; ii) MDC [23], an open-source tool for building Coarse-Grain Reconfigurable (CGR) multi-functional architectures from dataflow applications; iii) ARTICo³ [22], an academic framework for run-time reconfigurable multi-accelerator systems that enables data-level parallelism (i.e., multiple parallel replicas) and task-level parallelism (i.e., multiple parallel accelerators).

3.4 Environment

Heterogeneous reconfigurable systems combine processors, reconfigurable logic, and peripherals in diverse platform configurations. These are typically paired with different Operating Systems (OS's) to suit specific application requirements. The framework is designed to support a wide range of commercial platforms and operating systems, ensuring adaptability to user requirements.

Platform Supported reconfigurable platforms range from low-end SoCs with limited resources for edge computing to high-performance PCIe-based devices for cloud deployment. To support this diversity, the framework's hardware components are provided as Hardware Description Language (HDL)-based IPs with an AXI interface, enabling integration across most commercial platforms compatible with AXI interfaces.

Operating System The framework supports both bare-metal and Linux-based systems. It includes all necessary drivers and libraries, exposing a simple Application Programming Interface (API) for managing any monitoring setup. Components can be compiled for different processor architectures and Linux kernel versions, ensuring broad compatibility.

3.5 Extraction of the Measurements

Traces obtained with the monitor can be i) stored as binary files to be processed later, ii) placed in local buffers for run-time analysis, or iii) plotted using the provided visualization tool.

3.6 Monitor Customization

The framework supports a flexible composition of monitoring infrastructures. Table 1 lists tested component options, although the modularity of the proposed framework allows many others to be added with minimal effort.

Platform	OS	Power	Performance	Control	Acceleration
Pynq-Z1	Yocto-Linux	External board	Internal HW signals	PS	ARTiCo ³
Kria KV260 SoM	Custom Linux	On-chip ADCs	AXI bus	PL	MDC
Alveo U250	Petalinux	Platform-specific		PCIe	AMD Vitis
Zynq US+ ZCU102	Bare-metal				
Genesys 2					

Table 1: Configuration space.

As shown in Figure 1, during the configuration stage, hardware and software parameters are collected (e.g., from TCL scripts and config files), along with platform and OS details, to define the desired monitoring setup. At the end of the configuration, the hardware description monitoring infrastructure and the associated software stack (libraries and drivers) will be available.

The main steps to configure the framework, including custom additions, are outlined below.

Hardware design While any platform with an FPGA and a general-purpose core is supported by the framework, design automation is enhanced on AMD platforms, and integration is smoother when using a Linux OS. Power can be measured via on-board ADCs, if available, or through the external board provided. Finally, users must instantiate their HDL/HLS coprocessors in the FPGA, as they would normally do with a conventional design flow.

Monitoring IP configuration and connection The monitoring IP is instantiated and configured within the Vivado block design environment. Users can define whether to use the external power board, set the number of monitored signals, and allocate BRAM for trace storage. The IP must then be connected to the coprocessor’s `start/stop` signals or to the communication bus for performance tracking and synchronization. Identifying these signals is left to the user, as they are inherently dependent on the coprocessor architecture and interface.

APIs and execution On Linux-based systems, platform-independent scripts are provided to load the monitoring IP drivers via the standard `modprobe` system call, with the device tree updated accordingly. For bare-metal projects, the framework includes a C driver library. In both cases, a standard API is used to start and stop the monitoring infrastructure.

4 Evaluation of the Framework

The flexibility and compatibility of the framework are evaluated in this section. Multiple monitoring setups built by combining components from Table 1 are assessed in this section, ensuring that each option is available in at least one configuration. Note that this evaluation focuses on the monitoring framework itself, not the performance of the tasks or applications used in each use case.

4.1 Monitoring Configurations

Table 2 lists the evaluated configurations. Each was used to monitor a representative set of multi-domain hardware acceleration tasks (Table 3).

#	Platform	OS	Power	Performance	Control	Acceleration
1	Pynq-Z1	Custom Linux	External board	Internal HW signals	PS	ARTICo ³
2	Kria KV260 SoM	Yocto-Linux	On-chip ADCs	Internal HW signals	PS	MDC
3	Alveo U250	Custom Linux	Platform-specific	Internal HW signals	PCIe	ARTICo ³
4	Zynq US+ ZCU102	Petalinux	External board	AXI bus	PS	AMD Vitis
5	Genesys 2	Bare-metal	On-chip ADCs	Internal HW signals	PL	ARTICo ³

Table 2: Monitoring configurations to be evaluated.

Name	Description
BMM	A blocked version of matrix multiplication [22]
FFT	Recursive formulation of the Fast Fourier Transform [21]
CNN	A convolutional neural network [16]
AES	A common block cipher [21]

Table 3: Hardware acceleration task used for validation.

For each configuration, the power and performance traces captured during the validation tasks are presented graphically. Tasks may run multiple iterations to ensure clear visualization. The monitoring overhead (averaged over 1,000 executions) and resource utilization are also reported and discussed.

	Config. #1	Config. #2	Config. #3	Config. #4	Config. #5
Power Traces	65,536 samples	Software ³	Software ³	131,072 samples	32,768 samples
Performance	8 probes	2 probes	32 probes	32 probes ¹	8 probes
Traces	16,384 samples ²	16,384 samples ²	16,384 samples ²	4,096 samples ²	16,384 samples ²
LUTs	1,560	1,046	1,044	2,179	1,593
FFs	734	397	468	925	720
BRAMs	44	15.5	29	52	36

¹ Extracted from the AXI bus signals² A 32-bit timestamp is stored with every sample³ Captured and stored on the CPU, limited by the available memory

Table 4: Resource utilization of the monitor.

	Config. #1	Config. #2	Config. #3	Config. #4	Config. #5
Application	BMM	FFT	CNN	AES	BMM
Overhead	Capture	0%	0%	10.17%	13.97%
	Transfer	0.72%	11.11%	0.25%	0.30%
				0%	0%
				9.00%	0.08%

Table 5: Monitoring overhead.

Configuration #1 The Pynq-Z1 platform, featuring a Zynq-7000 SoC for edge computing, runs ARTICo³-based acceleration under a custom Linux on the PS. Performance is monitored via internal `start/stop` accelerator signals. As the board lacks on-chip ADCs, power consumption is measured using the external board on the main power rail. Figure 2 shows the power (top) and performance (bottom) traces for BMM and FFT, each using four replicas.

The external measurement board, with sampling rates up to 1 Msample/s, enables detailed capture of power waveforms, essential for power-aware applications. This high resolution reveals fine-grained power behavior, such as lower

power consumption while hardware acceleration is being used (after the rising edge of start signals), compared to data processing (after stop signals). Even processing stages can be visually distinguished. This precision comes at a resource cost, primarily in BRAMs (Table 4). Users can balance area usage and monitoring window size by tuning the number of samples collected. Table 5 shows the system overhead. Since trace capture is handled fully in hardware, system performance is unaffected. However, transferring data from BRAMs to the processor may vary in impact by application. For instance, the faster FFT generates more frequent traces than BMM, leading to a higher relative overhead.

Fig. 2: Results of configuration #1 – BMM (left) | FFT (right).

Configuration #2 This configuration uses the more performing Zynq UltraScale+ device available on the Kria KV260 platform, targeting dataflow task acceleration with MDC. Power is measured using the out-of-the-box on-board ADCs, with performance captured via internal `start/stop` signals. The system runs under a Yocto-based Linux on the PS.

Figure 3 shows power and performance traces for single-replica CNN and AES tasks. Due to faster kernels and the lower sampling rate of on-chip ADCs, the power waveforms are less detailed than when external measurements are used but still reveal apparent differences between active acceleration and idle periods. This setup is resource-efficient (Table 4), as only performance traces are stored in BRAMs. However, reading power data via software introduces non-negligible overhead (Table 5). Fortunately, this overhead is static and does not scale with the trace length, making it ideal for longer capture windows. For instance, the slightly longer CNN task shows a lower relative impact. Transfer overhead is minimal, since only sparse `start/stop` events are sent to the processor.

Fig. 3: Results of configuration #2 – CNN (left) | AES (right).

Configuration #3 This demonstration setup uses the Alveo U250, a high-end fog/cloud FPGA platform connected to a host PC via Peripheral Component Interconnect Express (PCIe)—demonstrating the framework’s compatibility with other PCIe-based devices. The system is controlled from a custom Linux

OS on the host. Hardware acceleration is implemented with ARTiCo³, running 16 replicas for BMM and FFT tasks (Figure 4), leveraging the platform’s abundant resources. For clarity, performance plots (from internal signals) show only two replicas. Since the Alveo U250 lacks on-chip ADCs, power is measured using Xilinx’s Card Management Subsystem (CMS) [27], illustrating the framework’s adaptability to external monitoring tools.

Interestingly, power traces show a weak correlation with performance signals due to the platform balance between static and dynamic power (up to 20W), which masks workload-specific variations. As shown in Table 4, resource usage is comparable to previous configurations. Thanks to its ample resources, this platform is ideal for long-term monitoring. The 1% capture overhead (Table 5) is due to periodic CMS accesses, while data transfer overhead is negligible, as it’s amortized over long application run times.

Fig. 4: Results of configuration #3 – BMM (left) | FFT (right).

Configuration #4 This setup uses a Zynq UltraScale+ on a ZCU102 board, demonstrating compatibility with AMD Vitis, the leading commercial acceleration framework. The system runs Petalinux, AMD’s embedded Linux, on the PS. Accelerators generated with Vitis are controlled via AXI buses using the Xilinx Runtime (XRT), fully integrated with the proposed monitoring framework.

The left-side plot of Figure 5 shows traces from a two-replica FFT, confirming the framework’s compatibility with AMD Vitis-based acceleration. Users can select any combination of AXI bus signals to monitor; the framework can then detect specific events (e.g., `start/stop` commands) and convert them into 1-bit performance traces. For power monitoring, the external board was used to measure consumption from dedicated shunt resistors on both the PS and PL.

Note the power spikes on the PS between consecutive stop and start events, caused by data transfers to/from accelerators, and the drop after the final stop, highlighting the end of hardware execution. In contrast, PL power remains stable, as the accelerators stay configured throughout the measurement window. Resource usage and overhead (Table 4, Table 5) are comparable to Configuration #1, since both use the same trace collection approach.

Configuration #5 This configuration uses a Kintex-7 FPGA on the Genesys 2 platform, featuring a RISC-V soft-core processor (CVA6 [28], OpenHW Group) implemented in the PL and running in bare-metal. It demonstrates the framework’s compatibility with soft-core processors from different architectures and bare-metal environments.

The right-side plot of Figure 5 shows a four-replica BMM executed with ARTiCo³. Performance traces are captured from internal hardware signals, while

power is measured via on-chip ADCs. Unlike Configuration #2, power monitoring is fully managed in hardware, as the platform lacks a PS and thus no software I²C manager. Resource usage is similar to Configurations #1 and #4 (Table 4). In terms of overhead (Table 5), the I²C-based power capture produces fewer traces than the SPI method, resulting in negligible transfer overhead. Additionally, since I²C access is handled in hardware, no run-time capture overhead is incurred—unlike in Configuration #2.

Fig. 5: Results of configurations #4 - FFT (left) and #5 - BMM (right).

Discussion The results demonstrate the framework’s high adaptability across platforms, enabling detailed performance and power analysis with minimal system impact. Users can flexibly balance power resolution, resource usage, and performance overhead based on their needs. The framework supports a wide range of platform/OS combinations, allowing tailored monitoring for hardware acceleration in diverse domains. External boards offer fine-grained power monitoring at a higher resource cost, while on-chip ADCs provide simpler, lightweight alternatives. Capture overhead is minimal, and transfer overhead depends on task duration and trace volume. The framework also supports further customization, for example, users can select more probes and trace samples for debugging or opt for a lightweight, lower-resolution approach for runtime processing. Overall, the framework offers a flexible, efficient solution for monitoring hardware acceleration in heterogeneous systems.

4.2 Accuracy and Synchronization of the Traces

Configuration #1 (Table 2) was used to evaluate the accuracy of power measurements and trace synchronization. A single-replica BMM accelerator was executed, capturing both power consumption (board supply) and performance traces (**start/stop** signals) via the monitoring framework. In parallel, the same signals were recorded with an oscilloscope, using a shunt resistor for power and a custom signal to indicate kernel activity. Figure 6 compares the monitoring infrastructure traces (left) with oscilloscope data (right). Aside from converting voltage to power, no processing was applied to the oscilloscope signals. The comparison shows minimal differences, confirming the framework’s high accuracy in both power measurement and synchronization.

5 Conclusions

This paper introduces a modular and composable framework for monitoring performance and power consumption in reconfigurable FPGA-based systems.

Fig. 6: Accuracy and trace synchronization – Monitor (left) | Oscilloscope (right). Its architecture leverages platform-agnostic interfaces to seamlessly integrate target-specific components (e.g., acceleration frameworks, ADCs, CPU cores, and FPGA boards), enabling flexible plug-and-play monitoring and tracing capabilities across diverse user-defined scenarios.

Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed framework can be tailored to various application requirements. It supports lightweight, low-overhead monitoring for real-time systems and high-resolution data acquisition through dedicated external hardware for precise execution profiling. This profiling capability facilitates data-driven modeling, prediction, and estimation of key run-time metrics, enhancing the system’s adaptability and performance analysis.

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